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Bhagat Singh's Revolutionary Ideology: Genesis and Growth

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The revolutionary life of Bhagat Singh is not only a source of inspiration for all of us but equally significant is that he stands as a lights house for the generations to come.

Shaheed Bhagat Singh, a legendary figure is undoubtedly one of the brightest star in the galaxy of freedom fighters of India. Neta ji Subhash Chandra Bose, while paying his tribute to Bhagat Singh in a speech delivered at New Delhi shortly after the latter's martyrdom said, "Bhagat Singh is not a person, but a symbol. He symbolizes the spirit of revolt that has taken place in the country"¹. The revolutionary life of Bhagat Singh is not only a source of inspiration for all of us but equally significant is that he stands as a lights house for the generations to come. The great martyr acquired unparallel stature and glory in the brief span of his life. He was not just a brave revolutionary activist but also a profound thinker and an ideologue with a keen sense of analysis that had long term visionary investment for the future of India. He was an able organiser and a clear headed thinker who could not only arouse the genuine patriotic emotions of the masses and also could orient them with his clear analytical thinking and the revolutionary ideology of those days. Not only did he himself personify the rare qualities of courage and sacrifice, he could also through words and deeds, instil those qualities in others.

The present paper attempts to analyse the role of early life and contemporary revolutionary activities which shaped Bhagat Singh's mind of growing age and could help him to evolve his own and independent revolutionary ideology. Though a compartmentalisation of a historical person is not possible but in order to fully understand Bhagat Singh as an ideologue and a political man it is essential to understand and analyse the initial phase of his life.

Bhagat Singh was born in a family with revolutionary traditions². His birth took place at a time when the political situation in the Punjab, was very tense due to the agitation against the colonisation act launched by Ajit Singh and Lala Lajput Rai, the well known revolutionaries. Some of the leaders even looked to driving the Britishers out of the country either by force or through

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close relations with contemporary Indian gadharities and revolutionaries such as Sachinder Nath Sanyal and Kartar Singh Sarabha. In 1907, he took part in the agitation against the Basi Doaba Canal Act and Colonization Act and was even arrested. Swaran Singh was also an ardent nationalist and a freedom fighter. He too joined and participated in the agitation against the colonization act. As a consequence, he was arrested and kept in central jail, Lahore. He developed tuberculosis and died in 1910 at the early age of 23. Vidyawati, the mother of Bhagat Singh was also an inspiring force behind Bhagat Singh. She could inculcate the sense of responsibility towards the nation and with the passage of time the environment at home helped Bhagat Singh to imbibe the value of patriotism and an unquestioning loyalty to the country.

Thus, a family background developed nationalist feeling in Bhagat Singh's mind set at a very early age of his life. At an early age of five, he would divide his playmates into two groups and would stage fights between them to promote the feeling of nationalism and to teach them that they have to expel the Britishers from India. The exile of his uncle, Ajit Singh in 1909, because of his nationalist views and his work in the struggle for freedom, made a deep impression on the mind of Bhagat Singh. How deep was that impression could be judged from the following talk. Ajit Singh's wife used to weep most of the time because of the exile of her husband, Bhagat Singh used to say, aunty do not weep, when I grow up, I will drive the Britishers out of India and bring my uncle back⁷.

Bhagat Singh joined the district primary school in 1916-17 having passed the 5th class from the village school; he joined the DAV school, Lahore. While at school he was good at studies⁸. In those days the entire atmosphere was charged with the combustible fall out of the legends of Ghadar Party heroes and martyrs. The restlessness which he inherited from his family mixed in with the air in which he was breathing. He was sensitive towards the most genuine cause of the freedom of the nation. Of all Bhagat Singh was greatly influenced by Kartar Singh Sarabha. The impact of Shahid Kartar Singh Sarabha's heroism and sacrifice on Bhagat Singh could be judged from the fact that when the latter was arrested a photograph of Kartar Singh was recovered from him. He always carried Sarabha's picture in his pocket and derived greater inspiration from the hero of his life. He always used to show that photograph to his mother and say "see mother, this is my hero, friend and companion"⁹.

The Russian revolution of 1917 had a world wide impact and was an epochal event which attracted the attention of the revolutionaries all over the world including Bhagat Singh in India. He read about the success of Russian revolution and even began to consider the Soviet Union as the state which was nearest to their ideal¹⁰. The sensitive and analytical mind of Bhagat Singh could sense the contradictions prevailing in the society. Needless to say it helped Bhagat Singh to develop a vision and make his own worldview regarding future formation of India. The Jalianwalla Bagh massacre left a deep imprint on the young impressionable mind of Bhagat Singh. He also drew inspirations from the revolutionaries of Kanpur and Uttar Pradesh. At that time Bhagat Singh was only 12 years old. But when he heard the news, he reached Amritsar instead of going to school and picked up a little soil in a phial. He reached home very late after the escaped, his elder sister informed him that his share of mangoes was waiting for him. Ordinarily, he would have jumped at them but that very piece of information appeared too mundane and remote to him. He took his sister aside, showed the phial stuffed with the holy soil and said, "the Britishers have massacred hundred of our man"¹¹.

While in college, Bhagat Singh came in contact with Bhagwati Charan Vohra, Sukhder, Yashpal, Ram Krishan and Tirath Ram but he was much impressed by Jai Chander Vidyalankar, his history teacher. His lectures on history of revolution and socialism influenced Bhagat Singh the most. Besides, special lectures were delivered in the college by Lala Lajpat Rai and Bhai Parmanand¹² and as a result of these lectures, he became conscious and even sensitive towards the issues of social and political nature of Indian Society.

The above discussion leads us to the conclusion that the objective and subjective conditions of those days influenced Bhagat Singh's thinking the most. For the times to come the tense and revolutionary situation had deep impact on his young and impressionable mind. The schooling and higher education, the discussions and deliberations in the educational institutions prepared the ground to design his own political ideology and to emerge as a serious 'ideologue' who could analyse the problems with a scientific methodology being confronted by the Indian society in those days. The situation at international level also moulded his vision and helped him to evolve an ideology based upon the principle of liberty, equality and justice, which will promote the basic principle of equalitarianism for future generation of India.

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